

Teaching English Vocabulary in Junior High School Students by Using Simulation Games

Ghina Salsabila Wahab^{1*}, Syamsu T², Lababa³, Sam Hermansyah⁴, Ernawati⁵
¹²³⁴Universitas Muhammadiyah Sidenreng Rappang, ⁵SMP Negeri 5
Maritengngae

Corresponding Author: Ghina Salsabila Wahab wahabghina9@gmail.com

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords: Simulation Games, English Vocabulary, English Learning Achievement

Received : 03, September

Revised : 17, September

Accepted: 20, October

©2023 Wahab, T, Lababa, Hermansyah, Ernawati: This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Atribusi 4.0 Internasional](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).

ABSTRACT

This study aimed to improve the English vocabulary of the Class Eight A students of SMP Negeri 5 Maritengngae by using Simulation Games.) With a population of 77 students from 3 classes, one class was selected where the Simulation Games were applied. The class which was selected was Class Eight A with 24 students which divided into 10 boys and 14 girls. To collect the data, the researcher used tests and non-tests instrument. Tests instruments included pretest and post test and non-tests instruments included questionnaire and documentation. Because the research is mix study (qualitative and quantitative study), that's why all the data that had been collected, were managed and explained by using quantitative and qualitative techniques. The students' responses were very good. This was shown by their responses to the statements in the questionnaire. There were 19 to 22 students or 79 % to 91.67 % students were Strongly Agree and Agree with the statements, such as: My English vocabulary increase after learning using Simulation Games, Simulation Games motivates me to learn, and so on. Because of the students' responses were very good, automatically the students enjoyed using Simulation Games in the learning process. The impact of this was the students' achievement were better after the application of Simulation Games.

INTRODUCTION

English as a Foreign Language (EFL) refers to teaching and learning of English in a setting in which English is neither widely used for communication among the nation, nor it is used as the medium of instruction. English taught to or used by non-native individuals. English is a foreign language in Indonesia because it is not spoken by all people in Indonesia. But people know well that English is an international language. It means that you can use the language all over the world. Many people, in Indonesia, say that English is very difficult because it is different from their native language. Panggabean (2015) explained that "...English is very different from Bahasa Indonesia in terms of phonology, morphology, and syntax."

A number of problems emerged in English teaching and learning at school, partly coming from students, partly from teachers, and partly from the school's facilities, namely, students' lack of vocabulary mastery, students' low concentration, students' low motivation, students' lack of discipline, students' boredom, speaking problem and shortage of teachers' training. Socio-linguistic research in the past few years has made educators more conscious of language functions and therefore has clarified one level of language teaching goals with greater precision. Specialized English is best learned as a second layer built upon a firm general English foundation. It may be appropriate, therefore, to conclude this with a consideration of the learning of English as a foreign/second language within the educational dimension. Clearly, not simply for the learner to be able to write to a foreign pen friend, to be able to calculate his income tax, or understand his domestic fuse-box, though these are all practical by-products of the learning process.

As other schools in Indonesia, UPT SMP Negeri 5 Maritengngae also includes English as a subject that must be learned by the students. The students learn English twice a week or four hours of lessons. English is the first foreign language taught in UPT SMP Negeri 5 Maritengngae. The official language of the students is Bahasa Bugis or Bugis language in getting along whether in their family environment, community or at school they use the Bugis language. But they sometimes use Indonesian, as a national language, to communicate with their teachers or friends. In learning English, students find many difficulties, for example difficulties in pronouncing English words, translating English words into Indonesian, using the right words to communicate, and so on. The students really lack of vocabulary and this is what really hinders students to communicate with friends or teachers. Students do not have a strong motivation to learn English. In teaching reading material, so that students understand the contents of the reading, sometimes the teacher has to translate it into their local language. English teachers must work hard to arouse students' enthusiasm for learning. Therefore, researchers conducted research with the intention of offering a way to learn English that can motivate students to learn English.

The language systems are needed to support learning the major skills, namely structure, vocabulary, grammar, and pronunciation. In learning English, the learner has to memorize some vocabulary to master the English

language. Black Hills State University (2006:4) stated that “Vocabulary or word meaning is one of the keys to comprehension. According to the statement above, no one can speak English without any vocabulary. The focus of this research is strategies for teaching vocabulary.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Vocabulary is the basic aspect of learning a language that learners should master. According to Wilkins in Thornbury (2002: 13) summed up that without vocabulary nothing can be conveyed. Based on the statement above. Similar to Krashen’s statement, (1998:155): “A vocabulary is a basic component in communication”. Based on the statement, we can conclude that vocabularies are fundamental to language. Vocabulary will be the first thing to develop language skill.

Vocabulary is a crucial part of learning English. Vocabulary plays important role in mastering language. According to Linse (2005:121) stated that vocabulary is a collection of words that an individual knows. Based on the statement above every one has to improve his or her vocabulary individually. Improving vocabulary in English is more difficult than learning vocabulary in Indonesia viewed. The difficulty lies in the meaning, writing, word use, and also pronunciation of the words.

However, some students in the school have a good vocabulary and the others lower. Some of the students can express their ideas in English while others can’t. In this case, I think the differences are caused by the strategies of teaching applied by the teacher. The students who have good vocabulary usually accepted the interesting strategies of teaching. Interesting strategies can improve mastering vocabulary effectively and quickly.

Games are widely used to engage students in learning. PhET (Moore, Chamberlain, Parson, and Perkins 2014), for instance, uses simulation to teach/learn concepts in areas like biology, chemistry, and physics and engage students through intuitive games. Yet, while games are used for teaching/learning complicated concepts and have somehow proven to be successful, we do not have many options for teaching/learning simulation use and creation. System Dynamics has what is perhaps one of the best-known games to learn the concept of delay and feedback: the beer distribution game (Sterman, 1989). However, this game is oriented to what could be considered motivated students, of appropriate age, who can grasp the positive implications of understanding the concepts of delay and feedback. Agent-based models have also been used under a game perspective with a similar goal of training older participants (Akhbari and Grigg 2013). In discrete-event simulations we can also consider the use of games for teaching/learning like logistics and supply chain. However, these topics are of less interest as the student/trainee gets younger.

Simulation games are games that tell or give an explanation about a flow of activities. They are widely enjoyed by all walks of life, because most of these games have no user age restrictions. Simulation games are included in the category of educational games that can provide a lesson or knowledge for its

users. Some examples of Android simulation games include Bus Simulator, Truck Simulator, Flight Pilot Simulator (Nugraha, 2018).

In addition, there are simulation educational games that combine simulation games and knowledge. They are dynamic technological tools created through delivery platforms to provide a scenario-based environment. Students work collaboratively to solve real-world situations and problems, thus ameliorating authentic and collaborative learning. Simulation game is a game genre that attempts to represent systems, machines, and experiences by using real world rules (Novak,2012:76).

METHODS

The subjects of this research was the students of UPT SMP Negeri 5 Maritengngae in 2022/2023 academic year. This research took one class as a subject to be investigated. Sample of the research were Class 8 A students of semester 1 in 2023/2024 academic year. The total students were 24 with the details.

Research is an important step to get new facts or additional information. In this research, there were some activities that had been executed. In this case, methodology was necessarily needed to make the research easy to conduct or to be effective. In this study, the researcher used mixed methods because besides this research requiring calculations using numbers to show whether there was an increase or not, it also required a detailed explanation of this research. In other words, the result of calculating the numbers (after applying tests and distributing questionnaire to the students) using quantitative method, then explained detail using qualitative method to make clear the result of the research.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

After checking the students' work, then the researcher put them in a table. The result were:

Table 1. The Students' Pretest Scores

Scores	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Classification
92 - 100	3	12	Excellent
82 - 91	5	21	Very Good
72 - 81	2	8	Good
62 - 71	7	29	Fairly Good
52 - 61	4	17	Poor
< 51	3	13	Very Poor
Total	24	100	

Figure 1. The Students' Pretest Scores

From the table above, we can see that there are 10 or 41 % students achieved the Minimum Achievement Criterion of 73 or more than that, and 14 or 59 % did not achieve the target. The students' scores are varied. All students' scores occupied all level. The highest percentage is on the Fairly Good level. It is 29 % students in that position. Then successively followed by Very Good, Poor, Excellent and Very Poor.

After giving Pretest and a series of teaching and learning activities, then the researcher applied the posttest on September 5th, 2023 to see the improvement of the students' knowledge after the use of Simulation Games in teaching and learning English vocabulary. The students' scores in the posttest stated below:

Table 2. The Students' Posttest Scores

Scores	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Classification
92 - 100	4	17	Excellent
82 - 91	6	25	Very Good
72 - 81	8	33	Good
62 - 71	5	21	Fairly Good
52 - 61	1	4	Poor
< 51			Very Poor
Total	24	100	

Figure 2. The Students' Posttest Scores

By looking at the table, we can changes of the students' scores. Firstly, no more students in Very Pool level. Secondly, Only 6 or 25 % students are under the minimum target. Next, there are 18 or 75 % students are above the minimum target. In detail, there are 4 or 17 % students in Excellent level, and then followed by 6 or 25 % students in Very Good level, 8 or 33 % studets in Good level, 5 or 21 % students in Fairly Good, and 1 or 4 % students in Poor level.

CONCLUSIONS

According to research findings, the researcher concludes that using Simulation Games in teaching English vocabulary to the Class 8 A students of UPT SMP Negeri 5 Maritengngae is more effective than without using Simulation Games. It can be seen from the results of the Pretest and the Posttest and the Questionnaire. This means that using Simulation Games in teaching vocabulary is effective in improving teaching and learning English process.

FURTHER STUDY

This research still has limitations so further research needs to be done on the topic "Teaching English Vocabulary in Junior High School Students by Using Simulation Games."

REFERENCES

Aksenova, Natalia V, et al. (2015). Developing Student's Motivation to Learn Foreign Language in Tertiary Classroom and Beyond. Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences MCSER Publishing (Vol 6 No 5 S1 September 2015). Rome-Italy.

- Anggraini, Dewi. (2020). Contribution of Vocabulary Mastery on News Writing Skill. Indonesian Department, FBS Universitas Negeri Padang, Padang, Sumatra Barat 25131, Indonesia. ICLLE 2020, Vol. 48.
- Ary, Donald, et al. (2010). Introduction to Research in Education. Wadsworth Cengage Learning. United State.
- Bakhsh, Sahar Ameer. (2016). Using Games as a Tool in Teaching Vocabulary to Young Learners. English Language Institute, King Abdul Aziz University, Jeddah, Saudi Arabia. English Language Teaching; Vol. 9, No. 7.
- Brophy, Jere. (2010). Motivating Students to Learn. Michigan State University. Taylor & Francis e-Librar
- Broughton, Geoffrey, et al. (2003). Teaching English as a Foreign Language. University of London Institute of Education. Routledge London an New York.
- Chonnia, Irannia Uma. Et. al. (2022). The Use of Squid Game Simulation for Challenging Students' Vocabulary Mastery. Faculty of Education, Muhammadiyah University of Jakarta, Jakarta. JOLLT Journal of Languages and Language Teaching. October 2022, Vol.10, No.4.

Creswell JW. (2010). *Research Design. Pendekatan Kualitatif, Kuantitatif dan Mixed*. Edisi Ketiga (Terjemahan). Pustaka Pelajar. Yogyakarta

De Smale, Stephanie. et. al. (2017). *The Effect of Simulations and Games on Learning Objectives in Tertiary Education: A Systematic Review*. Utrecht University. Conference Paper • June 2016.

Dhumal, Manjusha. (2015). *Gaming and Simulation in English Language Teaching: A Symbiotic Interweave Towards Language Efficiency*. November 2015, Vol. 8, No. 1.

Ebrahimzadeh, Mohsen. (2017). *Readers, Players, and Watchers: EFL Students' Vocabulary Acquisition through Digital Video Games* Department of Foreign Languages and Linguistics, Shiraz University, Fars, Iran. *English Language Teaching*; Vol. 10, No. 2.

E. Gredler, Margaret. (2017). *Educational Games and Simulations: A Technology in Search of A (Research) Paradigm*. South Carolina. Vlachopoulos and Makri *International Journal of Educational*.

Elmahdi, Omer Elsheikh Hago. et al. (2020). *Challenges for Methods of Teaching English Vocabulary to Non-native Students*. Department of Languages and Translation, Faculty of Science and Arts, Taibah University, Saudi Arabia *Advances in Social Sciences Research Journal*–Vol.7, No.5

Fahrurrozi, (2017). Improving Students' Vocabulary Mastery by Using Total Physical Response, Jakarta State University, Indonesia. English Language Teaching; Vol. 10, No. 3.

Fitriyani, Eka. (2016). The Effectiveness of Crossword Puzzle in Learning Vocabulary. Department of English Education Faculty of Educational Sciences Syarif Hidayatullah State Islamic University Jakarta. Indonesia.

Hamdaoui, Nabila, et. al. (2018). Modeling Learners in Educational Games: Relationship Between Playing and Learning Styles. sagepub.com/journalsPermissions.nav/DOI:10.1177/1046878118783804journals.sagepub.com/home/sag

Jenkins, Bakari. (2016). Using Simulation Games For Teaching And Learning Discrete Event Simulation. The Pruden Center for Industry and Technology 4169 Pruden Blvd. Suffolk, VA 23434, USA.

Kohnke, Lucas. (2020). Exploring Learner Perception, Experience and Motivation of Using a Mobile App in L2 Vocabulary Acquisition. The Hong Kong Polytechnic University, Hung Hom, Hong Kong. International Journal of Computer-Assisted Language Learning and Teaching Volume 10 • Issue 1 • January-March 2020.

Mawaddah, Yulia. (2010). Using Games in teaching Vocabulary. Department of English Education, Faculty of Tarbiyah and Teacher's Training, Syarif Hidayatullah State Islamic University. Jakarta, Indonesia.

Meihami, Bahram. et al. (2013). CALL in the Form of Simulation Games: Teaching English Vocabulary and Pronunciation through Sims. International Letters of Social and Humanistic Sciences (International Letters of Social and Humanistic Sciences), issue: 08 / 2013.

Meliana, Nia. Et. Al. (2018). Exploring Teacher's Strategies in Teaching Vocabulary. IAIN Syekh Nurjati Cirebon. June 2018. ELT-Echo, Volume 3, Number 1,

Ogoiua, & Wălina, et. Al. (2010). Testing a simulation game as a potential teaching method for a master course in human resources management. Romania. Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences 33 (2012) 845 - 849.

Panjaitan, Esra Elisabeth. Et. al. (2021). Vocabulary Teaching Strategies by EFL Teachers Of Junior High School Level. Universitas Prima Indonesia, Medan, Indonesia. Jurnal Pendidikan LLDIKTI Wilayah 1. December 2021, Vol. 1 No. 02

Rudianto, Gaguk, et. al. (2018). Pengajaran Kosa Kata bagi Mahasiswa EFL dengan menggunakan Game. Universitas Putera Batam. Jurnal Basis. Oktober 2018. Vol. 5 No. 2.

Vlachopoulos, Dimitrios , et. al. (2011). The effect of games and simulationson higher education: a systematic literature review. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences* 33 (2012) 845 – 849.

<https://www.idntimes.com/tech/games/rangga-dio-hayyunuski/game-bertema-restoran-c1c2>. Accessed on December 31st, 2022

<https://www.sukaon.com/10-game-bertema-sekolah-terbaik-di-ios-dan-android/>. School life simulator. Accessed on December 31st, 2022

<https://eprints.umm.ac.id/35685/4/jiptummpp-gdl-wikaramada-48245-4-chapter-i.pdf>. Accessed on January 1st, 2023

<http://researcharticles.com/index.php/descriptive-qualitative-research-design/>. Accessed on January 1st, 2023

<https://serupa.id/metode-penelitian-deskriptif-kualitatif-konsep-contoh/>. Accessed on January 1st, 2023

<https://byjus.com/physics/hypothesis/>. Accessed on January 1st, 2023

Wahab, T, Lababa, Hermansyah, Ernawati

<https://www.amongguru.com/pre-test-dan-post-test-pengertian-tujuan-serta-perbedaannya/>. Accessed on January 1st, 2023

<https://www.bosinformasi.web.id/2015/10/perbedaantestdannontest.html>. Accessed on January 1st, 2023

<https://www.google.com/search?client=firefoxbd&q=documentation+in+a+research>. Accessed on January 2nd, 2023.

<https://www.questionpro.com/blog/types-of-interviews/>. Accessed on January 13th, 2023.

<https://research-methodology.net/research-methods/qualitative-research/observation/>. Accessed on January 13th, 2023.

<https://www.atlassian.com/work-management/knowledgesharing/documentation/importance-of-documentation>. Accessed on January 13th, 2023.

<https://www.questionpro.com/blog/data-analysis-in-research/>. Accessed on January 15th, 2023